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PROBLEMS OF TRAINING PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS
SPECIALISTS AMONG WOMEN

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Kalit soʻz: tayyorlash, jismoniy madaniyat, sport, xotin-qizlar, kompleks, valeologiya, tarbiya, guruh, tibbiy xizmat Oʻzbekiston respublikasining jahonda goʻzal lohar xotin-qizlari bilan alohida oʻrni boʻrligi va bunday hulosa chiqarishimiz tarixiy manbalarda oʻz aksini topganligi bilan ahamyatlidir.

Ключевое слово: тренировка, физическая культура, спорт, женщины, комплекс, валеология, образование, группа, медицинское обслуживание. Республика Узбекистан занимает особое место в мире среди красивых долеых женщин, и наш вывод основан на исторических источниках. Значительно, что это нашел обратное.

Key word: training, physical culture, sports, women, complex, valeology, education, group, medical service. The fact that the Republic of Uzbekistan has a special place in the world with beautiful Lobar women and our conclusion is based on historical sources. z is significant in that it finds its reflection

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada yurtimizda xotin-qizlarning jismoniy madaniyatiga qaratilgan imkoniyatlar, xotin-qizlar oʻrtasida jismoniy madaniyat va sport mutaxasislarini tayyorlash muammolari toʻgʻrisida maʼlumotlar keltirilgan.

It is important that the Republic of Uzbekistan has a special place in the world with beautiful and handsome women and girls, and that our conclusion is reflected in historical sources. He worked hard in different fields and brought up children to become well-rounded people. The body of women and girls differs from that of men by a number of morphological and functional characteristics. This situation does not affect the physical activities they perform, therefore, it is necessary to take into account the specific characteristics of women's bodies when engaging in sports. .

There are stories and legends about Tomaris and Barchinoy in the oral works of our people. Compared to this, we see that in every political and social period, attention is paid to the comprehensive education of women and girls. It depends on how to organize and conduct sports training in order to train young sportswomen and improve their skills.

When organizing sports training, it is necessary to study the personal characteristics of female athletes. This plays a very important role in filling training groups with new and less qualified athletes. Highly skilled athletes train on the basis of a personal plan, that is, the more they train, the less effort they spend on physical exercises. The question arises why such an approach to this issue is necessary.

Uzbek women can work and develop in every field.

In fact, if we consider that more than half of our nation are Uzbek women of different ages, we can see that they are always superior to women of other nations with their hard work, regardless of any difficulties. That's why today's state policy is to train as many national women as possible in culture, sports and other fields and send them to educational schools to work. It should be implemented from a young age, in addition, it is necessary to organize a separate group of women in educational institutions and teach them with a teacher consisting of women and girls.

Such an approach to the issue is of national importance, because the factor of youth health is the basis of the preparation of the reserve of working rhesus for the national economy.

Brave female athletes of Uzbekistan are boldly entering international arenas

Nowadays, we need to increase the involvement of students in sports in order to further improve the health of students and young people. It is necessary to improve the health of

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young people, especially before graduating from school. This is also caused by the mobility of young people. Lack of mobility leads to the development of diseases such as obesity, diabetes, neurosis, flat heel, and deformity. Physical education is important in maintaining and strengthening movement activity and health of young people. Therefore, the comprehensive program on physical education should be directed to the comprehensive development of the growing generation, strengthening of health, increasing the work ability of students. At the same time, it should be mentioned that pedagogy is It is important to pay attention to the development of tools, methods and methodological instructions of physical training. In addition, it is necessary to take into account the need to protect and strengthen human health, the satisfaction he gets from physical training, and his interests.

In this regard, the diagnosis of individual capabilities with the help of a comprehensive assessment of human maturity should be the basis for achieving physical maturity. At the same time, physical development, body structure, physical and functional training - all this is the result of regular physical education training. From this, a person is satisfied in terms of strengthening his health. This, in turn, increases his physical and mental activity, as a result of learning and labor productivity increases. Thus, health should be looked at from the point of view of valeology. Because valeology is the science of forms, methods and tools of physical training that can prevent various diseases that may be caused by physical fitness, inactivity and harmful habits of a person.

It cannot be denied that the contribution of mothers in the development of society and in conducting socio-educational work in the family is high. Especially in the conditions of independence, the problems related to raising a child in the family are increasing more and more. There are reasons for this at one level or another. In our republic, the slogan "Healthy mother-healthy child" is deeply embedded in every family in terms of meaning and logic. It is important that mothers' healthy fertility is reflected in the content of state programs for the birth of healthy children from the youngest age. Health services are a priority for healthy mothers and healthy children. At the same time, it is no exaggeration to say that the theoretical and practical recommendations of doctors, pedagogues and experts on physical education are higher than any medicines.

A healthy child from a healthy mother

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Because all organs in a healthy body, especially the joints, bone and muscle systems that move, always need active movements. Physical exercises that provide them (gymnastics, sports, games, travel, etc.) activate and develop the tasks (function) of breathing, blood circulation, digestion and other necessary activities. These are all known general concepts. The main goals and tasks are to educate the physical fitness of local women, especially students and girls, to make some comments and recommendations about the most important measures to be taken in preparation for healthy motherhood, namely: 1. All types and the provision of general and special exercises for women in physical education classes in educational institutions of the categories is aimed at improving the physical fitness of the participants and directing them to perfection. 2. On the basis of the Healthy Generation state program, special tests of "Barchinoy" are aimed at maintaining health, raising physical fitness, increasing work ability, and performing various official, special services before the Motherland. 3. The organization of sports clubs, national teams, children's and youth sports schools (all types and categories), women's teams (teams), groups is not limited to achieving sports results, but healthy in the future. also aimed at being a mother. 4. Organization of health centers for women in sports facilities, private homes, hospitals, polyclinics and other areas is a sign of attention to them. 5. Women's and girls' spartakiades, To'maris games, Republican festivals, healthy family, father, mother and me sports games, competitions are aimed at expanding women's sports. It should be noted that such grandiose and very necessary events are conducted only at the level of the Republic, region and city. In densely populated Kurgan, large villages, such an event is used only on Navruz, the day of professions and harvest holidays.

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